

>>What's next?

In this letter:

- Short recap of Shamash Breakdown
- Recollection of Sun glyph connections
- Recap of the November 2019 reconnection events
 - ◆ Short comments on COVID connections
- Discussion of current arguments in GR, MOND, PEMC, and issues that lie ahead
- Recap of the issues of plasma lab experiment, critique of SAFIRE, desired next steps...
 - ◆ Zamora debunking incoming!

So what now? Shamash's Demise is only News to us; what does it really mean?

And how can lab work aid with satellite work?

February 2022

Best Viewed at: <https://bit.ly/34niUw3>

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM
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Re: What do we do now that the facts of the Younger Dryas event are starting to unfold?

From the Desk of Sf. Ramon Careaga, founder EPEMC, www.epemcgateway.com

Dear Readers,

I am working on the next MIMS paper, and it's more of a book¹. Plus a Strategy Series book is coming out², this week I assume. So what's next? Well, not the "Abandon Stellar Fusion" paper, I am afraid, nor the PEMS-2, nor the debunk of Zamora. For now the first Megafauna Extinction paper³ has to suffice. But I think by the end of spring I can get to the latter two, probably not the former. Why? I'm busy with real life things. However, I'll give this teaser:

Figure 1 - Gravity map, US. Note that the increased density (red) is happening east of the Appalachian mountains, including the Blue Ridge mountains of Virginia. And guess what is also there? **Magnetic** increase. So less matter, but more charge and magnetism (moving charge), and more gravity. Interesting.

Left to right on arrows: Sacramento valley (concentrated), not a volcano, The Rockies, not the Ozarks, not a fault line, Big South Fork geological wonderland, not the Blue Ridge, not

¹ The Threefold Sciences paper is relevant here because it has an entire section on OOPArts. When it become available, one can view it at: <https://bit.ly/3lsecCl>

² "To Loot a Burning House"

³ https://www.academia.edu/69494986/Plasmaglyphs_Introduction

Adirondacks but part of Appalachia; in other words it isn't always true that vallies equated increased surface gravity, or that mountains equate less!

Meanwhile; what can we talk about, and with some fun detail (and keep this short?) How about a short recounting of this image:

Figure 2 - Shamash from Columbian Rock Art. Notice that the formation of Neptune might have happened earlier, if that is Neptune's blue spot we are seeing. Note the panther stage, and correlate this with Gobekli Tepe. Also note that Shamash is in reverse (mirror) position to Gobekli Tepe Enclosure D. Indicating a different season (or orbital position) relative to the star. How long that year was we cannot tell. But as momentum is conserved, it is assumed we either orbited similarly, or our rotation rate must alter if the planet slows down, etc.

Again from left to right: leg formations just as at Gobekli Tepe, Panther/Lion head, again at GT, main star (Ra/EI), all are signs that the star was approached or our orbit was not stable, Neptune?/Great spot of some kind, two ends of two spheres opposing?, anode tufting of Proto-Saturn, “hatching” section, again we see a worldwide feature, bifurcation, Z-banding of Proto-Jupiter, bulge is also typical worldwide

Recall that the “sun” (Shamash) occupied the “middle” of the sky:

Figure 3 - “Zhong” 中 (Middle) etymology in Lu Shi Tong (L00595)

And in case you really forgot, this is the etymology for “sun” 日 ‘ri’ - Figure 4:

So now, this is not a random dot in a box; this is a direct connection of the sun glyph, hexagons, "solar", crescent motif, eye motif, cosmic pole motic, bull motif, egg motif, and Saturn.

Figure 5 - Jupiter South Pole (Juno mission) pre 2019

Figure 6 - Post November 2019

Figure 7 - Saturn's South Pole
([gif](#))

Figure 8 - Jupiter's North Pole, a massive connection to the Sun, now known ([gif](#))

Figure 9 - Jupiter's North Pole in closeup animation, rotational currents just visible in the aurorae. Note the differential velocities of the rotation of the cylinders. Please recall that both Jupiter and Saturn expel more heat than they absorb, but each year this number decreases. This is a data point which I intend to confirm and use, which has been buried by NASA quite significantly. ([gif](#))

So what is it we're seeing above? We're seeing a bifurcating star, with anode tufting of Proto-Saturn as the electric current of the star dropped off, and all its Cosmic Egg features covered in Addendum 2⁴, as well as the Z-banding of Proto-Jupiter which quickly became Jupiter, with a strong electric circuit connection to the Sun. Why Jupiter and not Saturn? Shamash split because of the stress put on it by the sun's coronasphere as we passed ever closer to it. The Sun needed only one connection. Jupiter fulfills that need and retains its 20,000x (of Earth) magnetosphere. However, it still has connections to Saturn. We saw this starting in September 2019, into November as the Birkeland current connected the two. Then the "conjunction" happened between December 16-20th, 2020 - and the bifurcation (or separation) wave was at max peaks from 2020 to expected 2024. The effects this is having in a nonlinear but not so unpredictable way, upon human thought patterns, Schumann Resonance⁵, sociological issues (such as yin/yang reversal in biological homo sapien species, are profound and interesting. But perhaps not a subject for this time (cancel culture), or in this form. However the author will remark on three things:

1. There appears to be a disproportionate effect upon the yin/female/Saturn principle
 - a. Two people I care about, women, have been diagnosed with cancer, and a number of women have seemed less than balanced of late.

⁴

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/354010454_Addendum_2_Megafauna_Extinction_Events_Update_to_the_Thunderbolt_Extinction_Model_the_Surprising_truth_of_the_Younger_Dryas_Event_that_Changes_Everything

⁵ Which has been out of whack for awhile:

<https://trinifinity8.com/why-is-earths-schumann-resonance-accelerating/>

2. This may or may not, just as likely, be related to the Venus archetype and/or Venus-within in females of the homo sapiens species.
3. The effects are not unrelated, though the relations are not clear as we do not yet know the current sheets in our solar system. Ben Davidson's hypothesis has not panned out.⁶ But masculine fear and fragility set aside, there does seem to be something pushing all people everywhere to speculate on larger conspiratorial forces and political ramifications. That includes me. I have felt this and done this. And I second guess myself often because pet theories require: data. We saw this in the failed 5G hypothesis for COVID⁷. However, while I said it was an obvious lab leak, I do not know if the power elite knew of the connections of Saturn to Jupiter, or of the brightness curve with Comet Atlas C4, or if there are even other plans in the works, beyond what has been determined in New Cold War⁸ and mimsical analysis.

The connections of Jupiter and Saturn to their moons, Io and Enceladus, are already established facts. Our interest here is in the establishment of the bifurcation's facts. Or at least making some speculation. To do this, let us reexamine the SAFIRE demonstrations (as well as make some suggestions for followup by the Aureon team⁹, and other labs/experimenters), and also let us utilize a new hybridized model of EU, SAM, LMH, and the author's own theories of HEGEME/PEMS, Cosmic Rearrangement, Two Way Entropy, and the mimsical diagrammatic insinuations of the "Big G". We will have to name this hybrid model at another time, unless writing this provides some brilliant insight.

Here are the components and what they bring to the table:

- **Electric Universe** (with MHD and plasma cosmology): source of energy, force/pressure for fusion, matching classical experimentation and lab examples, without use of "dark" universe hypotheses (which have been debunked)
- **Structured Atomic Model**: definition for the nucleus, including the elimination of neutrons, mechanism for gravity, and explanation for isotopic behaviors.
- **Liquid Metallic Hydrogen**: a crystalline liquid plasma condensate formed under the pressure, providing a real surface (and black body behavior) for the sun. However, without plasma ionic motion (current), it is unable to deal with magnetism. However it explains our issues in spectroscopy and optics.
 - It doesn't cover sunspot penumbras very well
- **Plasma-Electromagnetic Sky**: a theory of the interaction of various shells of plasma and charge layers, which enables an interaction between space and the Earth via the polarity of atmosphere and crustal membrane.
- **HEGEME**: The ability to account for more of the cataclysmic facts and expand the "laboratory" of geology, archaeology, and astrophysical phenomena

⁶

https://www.academia.edu/53139271/Strong_Letter_Response_to_Mr_Ben_Davidson_Suspicious_Observers_et_al

⁷

https://www.academia.edu/43190878/OPINION_On_Gurus_Electric_Universe_Predictions_Bio_electrics_Comet_5G_and_Futurism

⁸ https://www.academia.edu/51022722/Winning_the_New_Cold_War_World_War_3

⁹ <https://aureon.ca/>

- **“Hollow”** - as the core cannot possibly be iron, with gravity being absent in the core and the heavy elements slung outward to the outer shells, there is a liquid core, probably LMH or HHO/H₂O more likely.
- **Expanding** - able to deal with changing plate tectonic behaviors, etc. Does not eliminate subduction!
- **Growing** - able to deal with added mass and shrinking gravity seen in rock sampling and mythic facts, as well as archaeological situations like the Pregnant Stone, etc.
- **Electromagnetic Earth** - the facts of the transformer and capacitor behaviors of the Earth, and its PEMS related phenomenon, such as meteorology, or electro-volcanism.
- **Cosmic Rearrangement:** enables us to rely upon Intrinsic Redshift, gets rid of the debunked CMBR, and explains the “older than Big Bang” stars and other various OOPArts of astronomy.
- **Two Way Entropy:** source for Void/Counterspace energy¹⁰ (us), and source for Aether’s power (counterspace) which then explains how our observations of entropy are not a violation of infinite principles.
- **“Big G”:** enables us to look at the interactions of many facets, and compare & contrast their logical benefits. Not as separate doctrines, but interrelated (and correlated via fibonacci proofs) facts and phenomenon.

For example, let me go back to the reconnection of the two. How does this enable the comet Atlas C4 to promote the spread of SARS-cov-2? Technically speaking, it doesn’t. That’s still done by humans - conspiracy or natural, doesn't matter. What matters, from the Universe’s perspective, is simply the change to the Solar System Electric Circuit¹¹, and therefore the Planetary Electric Circuit. The facts must be this: the change (as Chinese Medicine asserts) must weaken the Charge Distributive Networks¹² (the “channels” or “meridians”), thereby weakening the immune system. This then enables particularly strong (or attuned) vectors to spread, leading to the production of more and more exosomes (messengers) which then share this “bad program” with already weakened people. Air, touch, fluids... secondary to the message’s field which is shared. This would be why I was able to tell the woman had COVID even as she handed the credit card back to me, and before I had “sampled” it yet (with my right nostril¹³).

What this does for our immediate future, as a species, is to force us to abandon the “dark universe” (including the Big Bang), in order to find out the true interconnected nature (electrical circuits) of all things, including geometries, etc. we will also need to fix General

¹⁰ https://www.academia.edu/63382042/_Something_from_Nothing_

¹¹

https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude

¹²

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330117614_Charge_Distribution_Networks_CDN_as_Meridians_Utilizing_conductivity_as_replacement_%27structure%27_for_meridians_comparison_with_neural_muscular_and_fascial_models

¹³ Easily cured with Xing Su San, which has hydroxyls and quinolones in two of the main herbs. It treats dryness.

Relativity, by moving to *Electric Relativity*, or PEMR, which will happen **soon**, within two years. MOND, already irrelevant, will be undermined as Kepler (and therefore Newtonian Mechanics) is explained completely in PEMF and various PEMC works, such as H. Alfven¹⁴, R. Juergens¹⁵, E. Lerner¹⁶, and as Weber's own works¹⁷ on electrodynamics are proved and unified. This will not be easy, but it's important that we (as a species) begin to recombine and improve on older models, and make a less-elegant-than-SUSY model, but still simplex in the same way. An area of mathematics that is used and engineered, *instead of worshiped*. No more cults of personalities. (You hear me, B. Davidson¹⁸?) No more "I have the entire answer" (you hear me D. LaPointe¹⁹?) No more haphazard, plasma-less classical electromagnetism or magnetism-only (you hear me, Distinti²⁰, Dollard²¹, and Wheeler²²?). The math will serve as a central theorem, based on (a) laboratory work, (b) experimental measurement, and (c) usable in practical, engineering situations and terms. **Just like: Steinmetz, Heaviside, Gauss, and Tesla²³**.

In order for this to be accomplished, aside from receiving the help of "giants" and retiring or semi-retired geniuses (you hear me, D. Scott²⁴?), the field will need to have improved SAFIRE v3 and SAFIRE like (redundant experimentation), terella and plasmoid (and fusor) experimentation with excellent langmuir probes. We also will need a systematized approach to electro geological experimentation, using defined, confirmed scientific compounds, both organic and inorganic, which then help us to define the terms of transmutation, petrification, and mineralization.

Changes that should happen versus pre 2022 experiments: inclusion of magnetism, adjustments in moisture and pressure, inclusion of extra anodes and cathodes, of motion, simulated energy bursts and more arcing, less continuous stationary streams of current, and more explosive and irradiative variables.

On top of this I will show in 2022, **definitively**, (as I did with J. Corsetti's Richat hypothesis) that Zamora et al. are wrong, and not the real leaders of the megafauna extinction discussions at all.

In fact they were already debunked in 2018, but I will repeat the points, covering all the new facts and new LiDAR. I will also demonstrate the correlations with respect to the previously mentioned gravity and magnetic anomalies, and in discussion of the vortitional observations which are "out of season" (like the January 2022 super tornado that destroyed Mayfield, KY.) This may require the reader to familiarize themselves with previous PEMS work, as well as the events of the September 2017 hurricane vs. 2 X-class solar flares events. It may require a bit of study of current electro geological work, which will be aided by a short paper and video source/table below:

¹⁴ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/pu-research/h-alfven>

¹⁵ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history/r-juergens>

¹⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sCwF6AYpljg>

¹⁷ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history/weber>

¹⁸ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/other-eu/s0>

¹⁹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/mag-universe/d-lapointe>

²⁰ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/other-eu/r-distinti>

²¹ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/other-eu/dollard>

²² <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/other-eu/k-wheeler>

²³ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/giants-of-eu-history>

²⁴ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/pemc/eu-general/thunderbolts-project/donald-scott>

Table 1 - Electro Geology At Present (2022) and evidence type

Structure/Location	EG Typology	Paper	Video or Website
Big Sink, Kentucky (56 craters, octagon)	Perattian Thunderbolt (cryptoexplosive)	Addendum 1	New Discovery (Mt. Horeb mound)
Hicks Dome, IL (magnetic anomaly)	Bolide + electrical (cryptoexplosive)	Pebble Beach TR	Crater formation in lab (Gable lab)
Garden of the Gods, IL	Liesegang Banding	Pebble Beach TR	Crater Formations cont
Knobs of Kentucky	Lichtenburg -900'	Culvertown TR & Addendum	Raised Dendritic Ridges
Red River Gorge (and Dogfoot hollow)	Alternate Layering	Pebble Beach TR	
Great Serpent Mound	Bolide + electrical (ce)	Megafauna - S plates	
Upheaval Dome, UT	Salt dome	Upheaval Dome Form.	Part 1 & Part 2
Shiprock, AZ	Central Anode	Shiprock / Barringer TR	Rock Monster Eagle
Pilot Knobs - KY, NC	1400-2400' anodes	Megafauna - Part 1	Yelverton Labs
Devil's Tower, WY	Anode	Ibid.	Surface Formation 1
Black Hills, SD	Cathode	Ibid.	Surface Formation 2
Wudang Shan, China	Cathode	Ibid.	Clay Formation
Stone Mountain, GA	Anode	Ibid.	Clay with Carbon
Looking Glass Rock NC	Sputtering Anode	Ibid.	Salt Water w/ Cymatics
Ayers Rock. Australia	Anode	Ibid.	
Big Hole, Kimberly SA	Kimberlite		Nature's Electrode
Barringer Crater, AZ	Octagonal Etch	Megafauna - Part 2	Impact Craters, TBP
Richat Structure, Africa	Birkeland Scar	Ashes of Atlantis 1	Steve Smith, TBP
Hudson Bay Craters	Birkeland Scar?	Megafauna - Intro	Electric Craters, TBP
"Carolina" Bays (varies)	Machine Discharge	Megafauna - Intro	
Melbourne Crater	Bolide + Electrical (ce)		Ep 3: Mega-Tsunami
Mars (various) lo "volcanism" Cryptovolcanism	Mostly discharge machining and electro-volcanism	Birkeland Superweb & Conquering the Solar System Megafauna - M Plates	Symbols of an Aliens Sky - Part 2

There are numerous other examples in Andy Hall's²⁵ work, on the Maars of Cenote²⁶, various triangular formations²⁷, but we aren't sure these are electrical so much as superheated wind²⁸ and wave formations, and a lengthy discussion at present about the "shield" volcanoes and of course instant petrification sites identified by geologists like P.M. Jupp²⁹ and R. Carlson³⁰. Finally, there are small subjects like iron "pipes" found in Asia and Kentucky (Sheltowee leyline).

Furthermore the reader should consider reviewing the [Magnetic Universe Theory](#) paper, as well as the [EPEMC Tables and Figures](#), and a quick glance across these products:

- [What is EPEMC?](#)
- [10 Reasons to Switch to EPEMC](#)
- [EPEMC Standards](#)
- [EPEMC Volunteer](#)
- [EU Primer](#)
- [Electric Universe Memo](#)
- [EPEMC & MIMS FAQ \(v2021\)](#)
- [What is Electric Geology?](#)³¹

Sincerely,
Sf. R. Careaga

²⁵ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=_3ITtdl_QRY

²⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4yccR12vDJM>

²⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fDIRMB3hVQM> & <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lTtvK1wyptU>

²⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pMPIjT6z8LA>

²⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Wmb0CSXF53w>

³⁰ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=G0Cp7DrvNLQ>

³¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mPcF40vBqzs>